

ART STUDIES

ON THE CURRICULUM OF ART EDUCATION

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Abstract

Doing a good job in the curriculum setting of art education will help to improve the quality and effect of preschool education, so as to improve the comprehensive literacy and learning ability of art education students and meet the diversified development needs of society and employers for talents. Art education is an important base for training preschool teachers, who are an important force to train the future socialist successors of the motherland. Therefore, it is necessary to strengthen the effective construction of art education courses and improve the comprehensive level of professional talents, which will help promote the sustainable development and innovation of China's education. Under this background, this paper briefly analyzes the curriculum setting strategy of pre-education major, hoping to effectively improve the teaching quality of art education courses and enhance the comprehensive quality of pre-school education talents.

Keywords: art education, curriculum, teaching innovation.

Introduction

At present, China's education is constantly developing and innovating, and all walks of life attach great importance to art education. Art education is mainly to train preschool teachers. Therefore, this major should carry out comprehensive curriculum reform, reverse the traditional backward talent training mode, actively do a good job in the curriculum setting of art education, and further improve relevant countermeasures, so as to effectively improve the scientificity and rationality of preschool education setting, help improve the professional skills and comprehensive quality of art education students, and meet the diversified development needs of society and employers for preschool education talents.

First, take employment teaching as the guidance, and do a good job in updating educational concepts.

At present, China's social economy is developing rapidly, and the requirements of society and employers for talents are also diversified. Technical talents have also become an important force to promote social development. Therefore, in order to effectively cultivate applied talents useful for social development, art education in colleges and universities should further strengthen the effective renewal of teaching concepts. By training teachers in educational work, the new teaching concepts will be implemented in the process of education and teaching, which will help improve the training quality of art education talents. In the teaching process, we should establish employment orientation and add operational and skill-based courses to the curriculum, which will help to ensure that the knowledge and skills learned by students can meet the diversified development needs of employers.

Second, strengthen the basic teaching of art education and innovate teaching methods

Art education is mainly composed of psychology, game theory, infant health care and many other knowledge points. Therefore, in the process of professional theory teaching, we should abandon the traditional cramming teaching mode, effectively apply multimedia technology to modern information teaching,

create a relaxed and pleasant classroom atmosphere, and use micro-lesson introduction method to optimize classroom teaching content, improve students' interest in preschool professional learning, and then improve classroom teaching quality.

Three, determine the goal of talent training, curriculum should be goal-oriented.

At present, the educational circles at home and abroad have clearly defined the training objectives of fine arts education talents in colleges and universities. In the process of preschool education, we should focus on cultivating students' professional skills, strengthen the effective combination of theory and practice, and cultivate comprehensive talents who can participate in educational work and social practice for the society. Therefore, schools should adhere to the principles of adaptability and stability and flexibility in curriculum setting. In the process of teaching, we can build a curriculum that conforms to the development trend of early childhood education. Remember not to change the curriculum at will, but set the curriculum content flexibly to meet the diversified development needs of teaching.

Fourth, actively create basic cultural courses to improve students' comprehensive quality.

In the new era, the curriculum of fine arts education in colleges and universities should realize diversified development, such as effectively integrating natural science, social science, humanities and other knowledge points. Through reasonable curriculum education guidance, students can establish a correct concept of development and help them form a sound personality. In the teaching process, we should focus on cultivating students' social relations, coordination and handling ability, strengthen the diversified setting of cultural basic courses, enrich students' cultural courses, and help to develop students' cultural learning career, thus improving students' comprehensive quality and promoting students' all-round development.

Fifth, establish practice base and optimize practice teaching process.

Because preschool education has many characteristics such as professionalism and practicality, we

should focus on strengthening students' practical skills training in the process of art education in order to improve students' application and practice level of theoretical knowledge. Schools should cooperate and communicate with kindergartens to provide practical bases for preschool education students, so that students can master theoretical knowledge and related skills in practice, find out the shortcomings in their own education and teaching management in practice, and correct them in time. At the same time, the school should also bring students into advanced kindergarten units for interactive communication. Scientific and perfect teaching facilities should be built inside the school, and simulated training rooms can be set up to provide students with specific space for theoretical and practical learning, so as to improve their professional ability.

Six, the development of hidden curriculum, to ensure that the curriculum is reasonable.

Schools should further improve the explicit curriculum, and at the same time actively develop hidden courses, such as holding teaching competitions and skill competitions, encouraging students to actively participate in social practice activities, or inviting famous teachers to hold lectures on campus. By excavating hidden courses, it is helpful to improve the scientificity and rationality of art education curriculum and effectively improve students' learning efficiency and quality.

Concluding remarks

To sum up, we can see that art education determines China's future education, so we should further improve the curriculum of art education in order to improve the quality of personnel training, help improve the development level and efficiency of China's social education, and further enrich the educational content.

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